

PROFESSIONAL FOOTBALL AS A CULTURAL PHENOMENON OF MODERN SOCIETY

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Abstract: *The article attempts to identify modern football in the process of competitive activity in all its diversity: from professional sports management to intra-football and around football segments of mass culture, in which fans are integral and inseparable part of it. The authors consider a subcultural phenomenon - a constructive support - as a tool the positive impact of cheerleading support on competitive outcomes during a football match. In this case, the set of the indicated components of the sports process forms a qualitatively new mechanism of its stakeholders.*

Keywords— professional football, popular culture, football and near-football subcultures, constructive support, complex modeling of socio-cultural objects and relationships, stakeholders of the modern sports process.

1. INTRODUCTION

At the turn of the second and third millennia of human history in modern social practice took shape, according to K. Aisenberg, a qualitatively new phenomenon of professional sports - a global cultural phenomenon [1, p. 91]. This statement is also true in relation to football as a kind of sports competition with the largest composition of its participants in the world - athletes and spectators. According to FIFA President J. Blatter, the total number of players in the world in May 2004 was 250 million people, which corresponds to 4.1% of the world's population [2, p. 10].

At the same time, the spectator audience of sports fans includes both fans in the stadiums directly during football matches and viewers of the worldwide television network, the growth of which is confirmed by the statistics of television inclusion. According to the marketing agency Futures + Entertainment, the official partner of FIFA, the number of TV viewers during the World Cup in Korea - Japan in 2002 was 28.8 billion, and the 2010 World Cup in South Africa was already about 40 billion. The statistical statement that every final match of the national teams is of participants in world championships: 1998 (France - Brazil), 2002 (Brazil - Germany), 2006 (Italy - France), 2010 (Holland - Spain) were watched by more than 700 million TV viewers, and this, in their queue allows us to assert that modern professional football represents a wide range of polyvalent sociocultural relations. Consequently, it becomes possible to consider the football cultural phenomenon (hereinafter - FCF) as the subject of our research as an integral part of the subcultural space developing on the basis of modern football.

The present study was built on the following working hypotheses:

- football cultural phenomenon appears in the post-industrial space of mass culture as a phenomenon of self-developing social models of sports and cultural processes;

- spectator-fans, professionally trained, can by their actions have a positive impact on the competitive result of a sporting event;

- the institutionalization of the socio-cultural subjects of the FCF is carried out on the set of interests of the participants in a sports competition ("stakeholders"), which form a positive sports result.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Particular attention in the framework of the FKF study deserves scientific works devoted directly to football as a sports discipline. However, it should be recognized that these studies were mostly carried out by teachers and

trainers of sports institutions and have as their subject the study of the pedagogical and physiological aspects of the organization of educational work and the preparation of children in sports specialties.

In recent years, starting in 2006, a number of works have appeared on various aspects of football:

- history of football (S. V. Butov, V. O. Nazarov); - general theory of football (M. D. Tovarovsky, B. G. Chirva);

- football in the sphere of culture (Istrate Petru, N. I. Svistunova, S. A. Khaleeva, V. A. Kiselev);

- football modeling (A. N. Tuganov, A. G. Plakhov, Yu. G. Tsuban, O. G. Savchenko);

- the professional status of a football player (A. N. Katulin, A. V. Portnov, S. A. Tukmanov);

- methodology and methodology for the development of football (G. M. Gadzhiev, V. I. Karpenko, D. V. Nikitin);

- the authority of the coach-teacher (Y.D. Ushkho);

- organization of the training process (Yu. V. Kolvakh, G.S. Lalakov);

- competitive activity (Gidara Saber ben Shadli, A. N. Grukalenko, Manuel Lishboa Teixeira Cautinho Garridou, G. S. Orlov, M. Yu. Grishin, L. V. Slutsky);

- development of the physical qualities of football players

(G.A. Aladashvili, Ben Said Nureddin Ben Mokhtar, D.O.Bulykin, V.E.Dayev, Mehdi Jamil Salekh, A.S. Lobov, G.L. Manevich, V.R. Milrud, I.N. Novokshenov, G. N. Semaeva, S. V. Titovets, S. T. Khachatryan);

- rehabilitation of football players (VM Bitkin, Sonia Maria Bordin, Fadi Mastov, Tran Quoc Tuan, Al Shamardin);

- selection selection, game orientation and specialization of football players (A.P. Zolotarev, Sirak Habtemariam Keleleau);

- work with the reserve of professional football (A. A. Suchilin);

- refereeing in football (A. V. Shibaev, P. N. Kulalae, A. D. Budogosky);

- prevention of football hooliganism (A. A. Meitin, D. Pilipenko);

- management and marketing in modern football (V. N. Alekseev, A. V. Tukmanov).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results of the literature review allow us to state that the philosophical understanding of the processes around football and inside it in today's practice is limited only to the analysis of the football subculture based on the interests of a small group of football fans and

hooligans (V. A. Viktorov, T. Yu. Deltsova, A. M. Ille, L. E. Kozlov, V. S. Kozlova, E. V. Platova, E. R. Salakhedinov, etc.).

Review of publications in the Russian media and the Internet on the topic of the football subculture and other youth informal movements convincingly demonstrates the growing interest in them.

It is important to note that only in five years (from 2005 to 2009) the volume of thematic electronic pages has grown a hundred times and amounted to more than 9 million information sites such as "football fans" and 823 thousand "youth informal associations (subcultures)". And this is only in one Russian search engine "Yandex"! A similar search in the Google system offers the soccer fans' sites for study in the amount of 65 million 400 thousand. electronic pages on which these constructs are mentioned.

According to the English writer Nick Hornby, the strata of football hooligans in the English Premier League make up no more than 5% of the total number of spectators attending stadiums does not reflect the entire spectrum of social phenomena aimed at establishing a system of interaction between sports and other types of society activities that form a new space of mass culture [3, p. 12]. It should nevertheless be noted that philosophical, and even more so a cultural perspective on the processes that determine the basic

foundations of these sociocultural phenomena in scientific practice, we have not noticed in the studied research works.

It is important to note that the modern scientific community pays serious attention to the aspects of managing the socio-cultural processes taking place in professional sports.

Examples of such research are presented in the works of the Kuwaiti Scientist H. Al-Mekaymi, who attempted to systematically understand some of the factors affecting the level of attendance by spectators of football matches in various countries, primarily in the countries of the Persian Gulf (Kuwait, Qatar, Bahrain and

UAE). The key factors, according to AlMekaimi, influencing the growth / decline of viewership, are: weak football club management; insufficient financial support of the club infrastructure; underdevelopment of the infrastructure itself; insufficient professional qualifications of players and coaches [4].

Analysis of the attendance at the stadiums of the elite European championships for the period from 2001 to 2007 shows that, in general, interest in the national championships remains quite high. In the 2006/07 season, gross attendance in England, Germany and Spain surpassed 11 million viewers (England 12.2; Spain 11.62; Germany 11.47). It should be noted that England has the lowest attendance in the last six seasons (the highest - 13.06 million viewers was in the 2001/02 season).

During the same period, Spain and Germany have steady growth in spectators attending football matches. In just six seasons of the football championships of the Spanish Example and the German Bundesliga, the number of spectators increased by 1.72 and 1.75 million people, respectively.

The same tendencies of increase in attendance of spectators can be traced in the matches of the football championship of France (Ligue 1). If in the 2001/02 season the number of spectators at the national championship was 4.27 million, then in the 2006/07 season the number of fans was already 8.31 million. The only exception was the 2005/06 season, when failure in growth dynamics. The attendance then amounted to 5.22 million viewers.

The situation is more complicated with the attendance dynamics in the Italian Serie A championship. Statistics show a drop in attendance at home matches of the Italian championship over the past two seasons (2005/06 - to 8.33 million spectators and 2006/07 - to 6.92 million spectators). This decline is due not so much to a decrease in the attractiveness of Italian football, but to the restrictive measures taken by the leadership of the Italian Football Federation in order to stop the hooliganism on the football fields. However, the final statistical results of the attendance of the Scudetos by Italian Tiffozi do not fully reflect the true level of development of football in Italy. Suffice it to note that it was in 2006 that the Italian national football team became the world champion, and Milan Milan became the best European team in the Champions League of the 2006/07 season, and at the end of 2007 - the best football club in the world.

The example of the Serie A championship, being an exception to the rule, only confirms the validity of the term “attendance” as the main criterion for determining interest in football matches.

The presented comparative dynamics of attendance at home matches of elite European championships suggests that in Europe in the second half of the twentieth century, rather large cheerleader strata were formed. This became possible primarily due to a whole range of UEFA measures - organizational, administrative, legal, etc., which led to the formation of a new environment at the stadiums, which made it possible to attract women and children to football matches. In almost all leading European football championships since the mid-1980s, there is a significant increase in both gross per season and average attendance per match.

The statistical data collected by the authors in the course of the research allow not only to systematize the obtained scientific material on the problems of the FCF, but also to consider the mechanism for the formation of a positive competitive result on the basis of professionally organized actions of the prepared cheerleader support group, which we will call a constructive support (hereinafter - CS).

The formation of the CS as a socio-cultural element within the football subculture required the study of social phenomena using the tools of applied systems analysis, which makes it possible to build a practical model of managing a “problem situation” based on the principles of improving intervention.

Understanding the states and development trends of the FCF in the context of mass culture requires a systematic representation of it as a socio-cultural object:

- modeling of sports processes of the organization, composition and structure of the FCF;
- formation of KS as a tool for achieving a positive sports result;
- the formation of a management system for the football society in the space of mass culture.

4. CONCLUSION

Socialization and globalization of modern professional football, all that is surrounds, as well as all the processes of its development in a competitive playing field, form a qualitatively different socio-cultural level of philosophical and sociological research in the field of physical culture and sports. It is this social basis, according to M. Ya. Saraf, that ensures the formation of: a) "a new sports-humanistic ideology capable of giving a systematic picture of sports in modern culture" [5,6], and b) new standards in the society of post-industrial society: the sphere of ideology, psychology, cultural studies, ethics, etc.

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